

Global Geodetic Observing System of the International Association of Geodesy

STATUS REPORT

11/14/2022

GGOS Bureau of Networks and Observations

Mike Pearlman and many others

Center for Astrophysics

Bureau

Current Status and Progress:

- Bureau presentations and posters at international meetings;
- Continued recruiting for the GGOS Affiliated Network;
- Covid and political situation froze cooperation with ROSCOSMOS through the MOC with ILRS and GGOS;
- Monitored network status; projected network evolution for the reference frame based on input from current and expected future participants, estimate performance capability 5 and 10 years ahead;
- Letters/documentation to support stations, current/ new missions, and analysis centers;
- Continued supporting the IAG cooperation with UNGGIM;
- Supported activities by the Standing Committees;

Plans:

- Continue advocating for the expansion and upgrade of the space geodesy network for the maintenance and improvement of the reference frame and other GGOS priorities; encourage partnerships to build and upgrade ground stations;
- Continue recruiting stations for the GGOS Affiliated Network;
- Continue monitored network status; project network evolution for the reference frame based on input from current and expected future participants,
- Continue the work of the Standing Committees;
- Letters/documentation to support stations, current/ new missions, and analysis centers, etc.
- Provide the opportunity for representatives from the Services and the Standing Committees to meet and share progress and plans; discuss issues of common interest; meetings at EGU, AGU, GGOS Days, etc.;

Services

- The Services continue to expand their networks as funding and conditions allow. New field stations are expanding the global network, and others are in process toward 2023 operations. Many presentations have been given by the services over the past year. But significant

geographic gaps still exist. Technology updates continue as funding permits and are evident in the newer SLR systems.

Standing Committees

- **Standing Committee on Performance Simulations & Architectural Trade-Offs (PLATO)**
(Daniela Thaller/BKG and Benjamin Maennel/GFZ)

Current Status and Progress:

- No specific session at EGU 2022, but many studies related to PLATO presented in various sessions
- Examples of recently finished and ongoing studies
 - Simulation studies on possible extension of SLR network (DGFI/TUM)
 - Simulation studies on differential LLR (IfE, Hannover)
 - Simulation studies on future GNSS constellations including new observation types (GFZ, TU Berlin)
 - Simulation studies on VLBI transmitter on Galileo (TU Vienna)
 - Simulation studies on dedicated co-location satellites, i.e. E-GRASP extended to GENESIS-1 (several groups)
 - Simulation studies on future (spherical) geodetic satellite configurations for SLR (Wroclaw University)
 - Testing optimized scheduling for VGOS (ETH Zurich)
 - Studies on best integration of VGOS and S/X-legacy network for VLBI in conjunction with ITRS realization 2020 (BKG, DGFI-TUM)
 - Pilot Project on improved analysis method for 24-h VLBI sessions with the focus on improved EOP estimation (TU Vienna, BKG, DGFI-TUM, NMA, OSO)
 - Studies on combination at observation level by using troposphere ties (ETH Zurich)

Plans:

- Re-activate pilot project on exchanging simulation data; SLR and VLBI simulations and subsequent processing results to be compared between software packages; period of CONT17 selected;
- Continue studies on best integration of VGOS and S/X-legacy network for VLBI as VGOS sessions are added
- Continue to encourage additional groups to contribute to PLATO
- Plan Face-to-face meeting, tentatively attached to EGU 2023

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- **Standing Committee on Data and Information (Nicholas Brown/GA, Sandra Blevins/NASA)**

Geoscience Australia (GA)

Current Status and Progress:

- Geoscience Australia is leading a global initiative to identify and meet user requirements for **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR)** geodetic data. This initiative is paying particular attention to ensuring the new and emerging user base of positioning information (e.g. location based services and intelligent transport services) have FAIR geodetic data;
- In recent months, GA and its collaborators have conducted a user requirements survey across a range of industrial and societal user sectors of geodetic data to identify critical gaps in standards identified in which could inhibit the uptake of precise positioning products. There were over 100 responses covering data standards scalability issues, lack of encoded metadata; technology, security and block chain technology, performance for demanding positioning applications, understanding the meaning of FAIR – Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable Data /Metadata;

Plans:

- Through a process of user consultation and engagement, provide user sectors (e.g. agriculture) with fit-for-purpose metadata profiles which meet their current and future requirements.
- Revise and expand the information model of GeodesyML to ensure the provided precise positioning data is FAIR.
- Progress GeodesyML development with assistance from the OGC Innovation Program.
- Develop, implement and test GeodesyML against current standard practice
- Welcome anyone who would like to assist in the development and refinement of GeodesyML to please contact us and get involved.

CDDIS

Current Status and Progress:

- Reprocessing and re-ingest of data and derived products for all CDDIS geodetic techniques (DORIS, GNSS, SLR, VLBI) has been completed for all CDDIS data collections. There is ongoing, clean-up work with some derived data product collections for this task. The Operations team is collaborating and working continuously to tie up all loose ends and complete the effort. All reprocessed granules have been pushed to the Common Metadata Repository so that collections and granules can be accessed and acquired via NASA Earthdata Search.
- CDDIS continues working with the NASA ESESES MEaSURES team at JPL and SIO: all new derived data product collections, including GNSS geodetic displacement time series, daily PPP troposphere estimates, transient earthquake data, and others, have been

ingested, archived, and made available at the CDDIS. These new collections include a CMR record, a CDDIS website landing page, and registered Digital Object Identifier (DOI).

- The CDDIS Management, Manager Patrick Michael and Deputy manager Sandra Blevins, facilitated a NASA Earthdata Webinar showcasing ESESES MEaSURES principal investigators and collections for the Earthdata community and beyond.

Plans

- The CDDIS continues to enhance and update all collections metadata in EOSDIS Common Metadata Repository with the guidance of the NASA IMPACT Analysis and Review of CMR (ARC) Project team.
- New CMR records for existing Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI) data and derived product collection have been create DOIs with associated landing pages are being developed.
- CDDIS has been given approval from HQ and ESDIS to start the effort to migrate to the Earthdata Cloud. CDDIS management will begin looking to acquire resources for this effort.
- **Standing Committee on Missions (Roland Pail/TUM, C.K. Shum/OSU)**

Current Status and Progress:

- Evaluating contribution of current and near-term satellite missions to the GGOS 2020 goals;
- Advocate the realization of future gravity field missions
- MOBILE (joint double-pair constellation of NASA (Mass Change Designated Observable (*MCDO*) study; co-funded by DLR) and ESA's Next-Generation Gravity Mission (NGGM)

Plans:

- Set-up a new concept of the Standing Committee to increase participation by potential members;
- Advocate and support national and international space agencies in their processes towards future gravity missions, by providing/exchange available technical information, and propose to support/participate in missions studies towards their realization;
- Communicate with Chinese IAG colleagues to seek advice and collaborations to advocate for possible availability of Chinese gravity mission data to the scientific community,
- Continue exchange with PLATO on joint interests and possible collaborations;

- **IERS Working Group on Site Survey and Co-locations (Ryan Hippenstiel/NGS)**

Activities

- Multiple tie surveys completed in the past two years (Mauna Kea, Ishioka, Yarragadee, Wetzell, Zeppelin, Male, Crozet, Futuna);
- Conducted deformation surveys at Ny-Alesund & Wetzell;
- Location of SAR reflectors during tie surveys;
- Testing completed for a system that collects deflection of the vertical (DoV) observations with a robotic total station. The specifications were passed to the team at Frankfurt and they were able to build an identical system and conduct testing at Onsala;
- Within the joint project GeoMetre, members determined the reference point of an SLR telescope at Wetzell, the Satellite Observing System Wetzell (SOS-W), using applied close-range photogrammetry instead of a polar measurement system;
- Multiple working group members made upgrades to software, reprocessed data, and streamlined workflows;

Plans

- Check tie discrepancy list from ITRF2020 and check results
- Continue research and studies concerning gravitational antenna deformation;
- Discuss formally locating InSAR reflectors, tide stations, etc.